

1 **A taste for numbers: *Caenorhabditis elegans* preference across bacterial species is driven by cell**
2 **numbers**

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6 **Abstract**

7 The study of animal behavior is reaching a level of detail that opens the door to quantitative models
8 covering almost any experimental condition. Such a comprehensive model may be achieved in a few
9 years for some simple organisms, such as the nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*, and a key component
10 to build it is consistent and systematic datasets covering wide ranges of conditions. Here we built such a
11 dataset for foraging in *C. elegans*, using a high-throughput experimental pipeline to map worm
12 occupancy of food patches of 12 different bacterial species and with densities ranging by 3 orders of
13 magnitude. Contrary to our expectations, we found that this dataset can be described with extreme
14 simplicity: Worm preference depends almost exclusively on bacterial density in terms of number of cells
15 per mm², and depends only weakly (or not at all) on other factors such as biomass content or bacterial
16 species. A common sigmoidal trend describes patch occupancy across our full density range and for all
17 bacterial species. These results indicate that the core foraging behavior of *C. elegans* is driven by the
18 number of cells consumed, rather than by chemical sensing and other stimuli.

19 **Introduction**

20 Due to the extreme complexity of animal behavior, our current understanding is largely fragmentary.
21 Most behaviors that animals follow in the course of their lives have been described qualitatively, but
22 quantitative and predictive descriptions are possible only in relatively simple and strictly controlled
23 situations. Small deviations from these stereotyped situations (often trivial ones, such as small
24 geometrical changes in a setup) may lead to large and unpredictable changes in behavior. Given the
25 complexity of natural environments, our ability to make meaningful predictions remains very limited.

26 However, recent technological developments are opening unprecedented experimental access,
27 unlocking a new level in the study of animal behavior. First, new observational techniques, such as
28 automated videotracking (1) or automated analysis of posture (2) provide behavioral data with
29 unprecedented throughput and quality. Second, neural exploration and manipulation techniques such
30 as in-vivo calcium imaging (3, 4) or optogenetics [REFS] provide detailed information about the activity
31 of the neural circuits responsible for each behavior. Third, theoretical analysis provides explanations
32 about proximal and distal causes of behavior [REFS], and is now aided by powerful numerical tools and
33 by Machine Learning techniques capable of making predictions beyond the abilities of the human brain
34 (5, 6). The combination of these techniques makes it possible to advance one step further in our
35 understanding of animal behavior, from stereotyped experiment to comprehensive models that can
36 describe—and predict—the behavior of an animal in any possible scenario. While this type of

¹ Important contributions have been made by researchers who are not named in the current author list. Their names are omitted from this draft because they did not yet have the chance to approve it. The author list will be updated in a later version.

37 comprehensive model is still far away for most animals, it is within our reach for the simplest and best
38 studied model organisms, such as *Drosophila melanogaster* and *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

39 *Caenorhabditis elegans* may be the first relatively complex animal for which such a complete behavioral
40 model can be built. *C. elegans* is a 1-mm long nematode, whose nervous system comprises around 300
41 neurons and is fully mapped (7). It is transparent, and it's possible to measure the activity of almost
42 every single neuron simultaneously while the worm is moving freely (3, 8). The neural circuits
43 responsible for many of its behaviors, such as associative learning or chemotaxis, are understood down
44 to the role of individual neurons (9–12). Thanks to this amazing level of understanding, work is
45 underway to build a model that derives *C. elegans*' behavior from a neuron-by-neuron simulation of its
46 neural circuit (13). Without the need to reach the level of simulating the full neural network,
47 quantitative models cover many *C. elegans*' behaviors, including exploration (14–17), chemotaxis (18,
48 19), thermotaxis (19), response to mechanical stimuli [REFS], and response to food (20–22).

49 OTHER PAPERS ON FORAGING:

50 Despite this impressive level of understanding, most previous studies are based on stereotyped
51 experiments that cover a narrow range of conditions, typically chosen to test one specific hypothesis.
52 For the case of foraging, the vast majority of studies focus on a single type of food, the bacterium
53 *Escherichia coli* OP50, and a single density (typically very high) [REFS]. Some studies have investigated
54 different densities for one bacterial species (23), and others have investigated different species without
55 controlling for food density (24, 25), but no systematic and consistent exploration has been made. This
56 lack of experimental datasets that cover a wide range of conditions systematically and consistently is an
57 important gap in our ability to build unified models.

58 To address this gap we characterized the response of *C. elegans* to different types of food, covering 12
59 different bacterial species and all relevant densities, spanning over more than 3 orders of magnitude for
60 each species. We chose response to food among all possible behaviors because it's already well studied
61 qualitatively (and quantitatively for certain conditions) [REFS], its underlying neural circuits are well
62 characterized [REFS], and has a clear and easily measurable impact in the animal's fitness [REFS]. Our
63 study involved more than 20000 worms on more than 2300 experimental arenas to test 64 different
64 experimental conditions with enough accuracy. We achieved this level of throughput with a custom-
65 built high-throughput experimental pipeline. We found that *C. elegans* response to all bacterial species
66 can be described in surprisingly simple terms: *C. elegans* response seems to be driven almost exclusively
67 about the number of bacterial cells encountered, regardless of the bacterial species.

68 **Results**

69 **Food preference follows a sigmoidal trend**

70 Our experimental setup consisted of plates with 5 food patches of different densities arranged as a
71 regular pentagon (**Figure 1A**). *C. elegans* is a bacteriophage, so each food patch was a drop of bacterial
72 culture whose density had been carefully adjusted by measuring its optical density (OD) with a
73 spectrophotometer. The bacterial drops dried on the plate overnight in conditions that prevented
74 bacterial growth (absence of nutrients for the bacteria and presence of bacteriostatic antibiotics), so the
75 density experienced by the worms was the same as the one measured the day before. Approximately 10
76 young adult worms were placed at the center of the plate, equidistant to all food patches, allowed to

77 explore for 2 hours, and then photographed. In order to ensure repeatability and sufficient throughput,
78 both the food patches and the worms were placed on the plate by a pipetting robot (see **Methods** for
79 further details).

80 We first studied the response to *Escherichia coli* OP50, which is the most common bacterium used to
81 feed *C. elegans* in the lab. In order to study a wide range of bacterial densities, we designed 6
82 experimental conditions, each of them containing 5 food patches with densities changing by 2-fold
83 increments. These 6 conditions covered overlapping portions of the density range (**Figure 1B**, colors)
84 and to compare results from these separate experiments we always report a relative number of worms,
85 N/N_{ref} , which is the number of worms found at each density (N), divided by the number we would find
86 at a reference density (N_{ref}) (see **Methods**).

87 We found that the relative number of worms per food patch grows monotonically with its density,
88 following a sigmoidal shape. This sigmoid stretches over more than 3 orders of magnitude of bacterial
89 density, with high-density patches attracting populations more than 100 times larger than low-density
90 patches (**Figure 1B**).

91 **A simple sigmoid fits the data**

92 Our data were well described by the equation

$$93 \quad \frac{N}{N_{\text{ref}}} = H \frac{1+4(D/D_0)^k}{H^2+4(D/D_0)^k}, \quad [1]$$

94 where N is the number of worms in a food patch of density D . N_{ref} is the number of worms in a food
95 patch of a reference density, which we chose to be at the sigmoid's midpoint. Therefore, $\frac{N}{N_{\text{ref}}}$ is the
96 relative number of worms in the food patch. H controls the height of the sigmoid, being the ratio
97 between its highest point and its midpoint. D_0 controls the sigmoid's horizontal position, being the
98 density at which the relative number of worms reaches 5-fold the low-density baseline. k controls the
99 sigmoid's growth rate, being the slope at its midpoint in a double-logarithmic plot (**Figure 1C**).

100 We fitted the three parameters of our sigmoid (H , k and D_0) to our experimental data (see **Methods**),
101 obtaining a remarkably good agreement (**Figure 1B**, black line).

102

103

104 **Figure 1. *C. elegans*' response to bacterial density follows a sigmoidal trend. (A)** Experimental scheme: Worms
 105 are placed at the center of a regular pentagon formed by 5 food patches of different densities. After 2 hours of
 106 exploration, worms located at each food patch are counted. **(B)** Relative number of worms found at each food patch
 107 (N/N_{ref}), as a function of bacterial density in the food patch (D). Dots: Experimental data for *E. coli* OP50; errorbars
 108 show the 95% confidence interval. Each color represents one separate condition with 5 food patches. Data points
 109 falling on the same density have been slightly displaced horizontally for clarity. Black line: Fitted sigmoid, following
 110 **Equation 1. (C)** Explanation of sigmoid's parameters in **Equation 1**.

111

112

113 ***C. elegans*' response to all bacterial species follows the same trend**

114 To investigate whether our results are applicable to different bacterial strains, we repeated our
 115 experiments with 12 different ones. Five of these strains are common in *C. elegans* studies (including
 116 another strain of *E. coli* and also *Serratia marcescens*, which is a known pathogen of *C. elegans*). The
 117 remaining 7 strains are soil bacteria that we isolated from the gut of *C. elegans* worms (see **Methods**).

118 We found that the response of *C. elegans* to all bacterial species are well described by sigmoids that
 119 follow **Equation 1 (Figure 2A and Figure S1)**. To quantify the goodness of this fit in a way independent of
 120 the normalization method used in **Figure 2A**, we took each separate experimental 5-patch condition,
 121 and computed the proportion of worms that reached each food patch (i.e. we normalized with the total
 122 number of worms used for that condition, instead of the number of worms found at a patch of a
 123 reference density). Then, we compared these proportions with the ones predicted by our sigmoids,
 124 finding a very good agreement (**Figure 2B**).

125 This result was surprising, since previous studies presented compelling evidence that some less-
 126 preferred bacteria were hard to eat for *C. elegans* (25). If this was the case, we would not expect that
 127 increasing the density could fully compensate the effect of being hard to eat, yet this is what we find.
 128 More surprising still, we found the same trend for *S. marcescens*, which is a pathogen of *C. elegans*, and
 129 actively avoided by the worms (26). An important difference with previous results arises from our
 130 experimental conditions, in which bacteriostatic antibiotics prevent bacterial growth and inhibit their
 131 metabolism, in particular preventing *S. marcescens* from producing the toxins that trigger avoidance in
 132 *C. elegans*. These experimental conditions decouple the effect of these toxins and other metabolites
 133 from the effect of bacterial consumption itself, and show a core foraging behavior of *C. elegans*, which is
 134 remarkably similar across all the bacterial species that we studied.

135 ***C. elegans* responds to an effective bacterial density ($\frac{D}{D_0}$)**

136 The sigmoids shown in **Figure 2A** look remarkably similar, their biggest difference being a horizontal
 137 shift. This shift is controlled by D_0 , which is the bacterial density at which worms start responding to a
 138 given species (specifically, the density at which they are 5-fold times more attracted than to a zero-
 139 density patch). We found up to 50-fold differences in D_0 across species (**Figure 2C**), meaning that that a
 140 food patch with OD=0.01 of a highly attractive species, such as *E. coli* OP50, will be as attractive as a
 141 food patch with 50 times higher concentration (OD=0.5) of a less attractive species, such as *B.*
 142 *megaterium* DA1880.

143 We hypothesized that *C. elegans* may experience an effective density for each bacterial species, which
 144 we could compute by dividing bacterial density over D_0 for each species. To test this hypothesis, we re-
 145 plotted the experimental data as a function of this effective density, D/D_0 . Consistent with our
 146 hypothesis, we found that this simple re-scaling of bacterial density collapses all experimental data into
 147 a single sigmoid (**Figure 2D**).

148 We also found differences in the values of H and k that provide the best fit to each species (as can be
 149 seen in **Figure 2A,D**, where each sigmoid has different height and slope). Although these differences are
 150 sometimes statistically significant (**Figure S2**), these two parameters have far less explanatory power
 151 than D_0 . Therefore, we can use common values of $H = 146$ and $k = 1.4$ for all bacterial species and still
 152 obtain a relatively good agreement with the experimental data (**Figure 2D**, black line).

153

154 **Figure 2. *C. elegans*' response follows the same trend for all bacterial species.** Color and shape of markers
 155 identify bacterial species, following the legend in box A. **(A)** Relative number of worms found at each food patch
 156 (N/N_{ref}), as a function of bacterial density in the food patch (D). Dots: Experimental data; errorbars were omitted for
 157 clarity (they can be seen in **Figure S1**). Lines: Best fit of **Equation 1** for each species (see **Figure S2** for sigmoids'
 158 parameters). **(B)** Measured proportion of worms in each food patch, versus proportion predicted using Equation 1 for
 159 each species. Errorbars show the 95% confidence interval. **(C)** Best-fitting D_0 for each species. Error bars show the
 160 95% confidence interval. **(D)** Same as (A), but as a function of effective density, D/D_0 (i.e. the bacterial density for
 161 each species has been divided over its corresponding D_0). Black line: **Equation 1** with $H = 146$, $k = 1.4$, and
 162 $D_0 = 1$.

163

164 **Preference correlates with fitness gained from each species**

165 Previous studies have shown that *C. elegans* preference for certain bacterial strains correlates with the
166 fitness benefit obtained from them (25). To test this principle in our dataset, we measured fitness
167 benefit as a function of food density for our bacterial species (see **Methods**), and found that it increases
168 sharply at a given food density that we call D_{fitness} (**Figure 3A, inset, and Figure S3**).

169 If food choice was driven by the fitness benefit obtained from each species, D_0 and D_{fitness} should be
170 proportional (black line in **Figure 3A**). Preliminary results indicate that they might be proportional
171 (**Figure 3A**), but we are still analyzing the full dataset.

172 If this result is confirmed, it would mean that the effective density that worms are using to judge the
173 value of each food patch is indeed a good metric of the benefit they obtain from it [This analysis is still
174 ongoing, but it's not critical for our main result]. Then, what makes some bacterial species be more
175 beneficial than others?

176 **Biomass content does not drive food choice**

177 We hypothesized that the amount of food actually available for the worms might be different for
178 different species, even at the same optical density (OD): OD measures the amount of light absorbed by a
179 bacterial culture, and for a given bacterial strain OD is almost perfectly proportional to the amount of
180 cells present in a microliter of culture. However, different bacterial strains have different cell size, shape
181 and composition, which affect light transmission through the culture. Therefore, cultures of different
182 species at the same optical density may have different actual density.

183 To measure the actual amount of food provided by each bacterial species, we determined the relation
184 between biomass content and OD for each bacterial species. We did this by measuring the weight of dry
185 biomass left after evaporating all the water contained in 1 L of bacterial culture at OD=1 (see **Methods**).
186 If biomass differences were to explain our results, we should find an inverse relationship between
187 biomass content and D_0 (black line in **Figure 3B**): Species with twice as much biomass at OD=1 should
188 have an effective density twice as large, and therefore their D_0 should be halved.

189 While we did find a negative correlation between biomass content and D_0 , this correlation is far too
190 weak to explain the differences across bacterial species (**Figure 3B**). Therefore, biomass amount is not
191 driving food choice in *C. elegans*.

192 **Cell number drives food choice**

193 Finally, we hypothesized that number of cells might be driving the preference. For the same reasons
194 discussed in the previous section, different bacterial species will have different numbers of cells per
195 microliter at the same OD. To determine the actual number of cells per microliter, we determined the
196 number of viable cells (Colony Forming Units) in cultures of each bacterial species. We combined these
197 measurements with microscopic observations, to control for cases in which aggregates of several
198 bacteria may be confused for a single cell (see **Methods**). As for biomass, we expected to find an inverse
199 relation between the amount of cells per microliter at OD=1 for each of our bacterial species and their
200 D_0 (black line in **Figure 2C**).

201 We did find an excellent inverse correlation between cell density at OD=1 and D_0 , with the exact slope
202 that we expected (**Figure 3C**). This result indicates that the "effective density" that drives *C. elegans*

203 behavior is simply bacterial density, but measured in number of cells per unit of volume (which is
204 equivalent to number of cells per unit of surface once the bacteria are placed on the surface of the agar
205 plate). We confirmed this fact by plotting our original data with the bacterial density measured in
206 cells/mm², and finding that indeed all sigmoids collapse to great extent (**Figure 3D**).

207 It's worth emphasizing the fundamental difference between **Figure 2D** and **Figure 3D**. In **Figure 2D**,
208 sigmoids are aligned horizontally using D_0 , which is a parameter extracted from the sigmoids
209 themselves. In contrast, **Figure 3D** has no active horizontal alignment: The data are simply plotted as a
210 function of bacterial density measured in units of cells/mm², and the transformation between OD and
211 cells/mm² was done using standard microbiology techniques, which were independent of our behavioral
212 experiments.

213

214

215 **Figure 3: The number of bacteria per unit surface drives *C. elegans*' response to food.** Color and shape of
 216 markers identify bacterial species, following the legend in **Figure 2A**. **(A) Inset:** Number of eggs laid by an individual
 217 after 5 hours on a food patch, as a function of the density of the food patch. Each species is characterized by the
 218 density at which the number of eggs increases sharply, D_{fitness} (asterisks). **Main panel:** Density at which the
 219 number of eggs increases sharply (D_{fitness}), versus density at which worms start reacting to the food (D_0), for each
 220 bacterial species. [This panel is provisional—reanalysis ongoing] **(B)** Biomass content for each species at OD=1,
 221 versus D_0 for each species. Black line: Inverse relation that would indicate that biomass content is responsible for
 222 the observed differences in D_0 . **(C)** Number of cells per unit volume at OD=1 for each species, versus D_0 for each
 223 species. Black line: Inverse relation that would indicate that the number of cells is responsible for the observed
 224 differences in D_0 . **(D)** Relative number of worms found at each food patch (N/N_{ref}), as a function of bacterial density
 225 (measured in cells/mm²) in the food patch.

226 **Response to mixed food patches confirm our results**

227 Our results indicate that *C. elegans* simply measures the number of bacteria encountered per unit
228 surface when deciding whether to keep exploiting a food patch or to leave it. This result raises an
229 interesting prediction, which in turn provides a stronger test of our hypotheses. A worm exploring a
230 food patch where two different bacterial strains are mixed will be simultaneously exposed to both. Any
231 factors such as different cell composition, different cell size or hardness (which may make one species
232 harder to eat), or different metabolites, will be perceived near-simultaneously. We don't know how
233 these factors might be combined, so if they play an important role it would be hard to predict *C.*
234 *elegans'* response to a mixed food patch. The best we can do is to define a reasonable null model,
235 assuming that the response to a mixed food patch will be an average of the responses to the
236 corresponding pure patches (see **Methods**). For a 50:50 mixture of two species, we define our null
237 model as any result between the arithmetic and the geometric means of the responses to each species
238 separately (**Figure 4A**).

239 In contrast, if *C. elegans'* response is determined by the effective density of the food patch, we can
240 predict the response to any mixed patch, by computing its effective density (i.e. the number of
241 cells/mm², counting both species), and use our sigmoidal model to predict the worm's response to it
242 (**Figure 4B**). By choosing pairs of bacterial species with very different D_0 (and hence very different
243 conversion between OD and cells/mm²), we can have cases in which this predicted response is very
244 different from the null model (compare predictions for **Figure 4A** and **Figure 4B**).

245 To test these predictions, we performed experiments with food patches containing mixtures of CR266,
246 which has a high D_0 , and DA1885, which has a low D_0 (**Figure 2C**). We prepared cultures at OD=0.5 for
247 both species, and prepared 5 mixtures with ratios DA1885:CR266 of 0:1, 0.125:0.875, 0.25:0.75, 0.5:0.5,
248 and 1:0. Given that both pure cultures had OD=0.5, all 5 mixtures also had OD=0.5 (range 0.49 to 0.51).
249 We then run our usual experiment, letting worms choose among 5 food patches made from these 5
250 mixtures (**Figure 4C**). In order to eliminate the effects of day-to-day variability, we also re-measured the
251 sigmoids for these two species the same day as we performed the mixed-drop experiment (**Figure S1**),
252 and we used these re-measured sigmoids to perform our prediction (see **Methods**).

253 Our experimental results follow our predictions, and clearly reject the null model (**Figure 4D**). Besides
254 the pair of species presented here, we measured another three pairs (a total of four pairs). In three out
255 of four cases we obtained a good quantitative agreement between the data and our prediction (**Figure**
256 **S4**). The remaining pair did not show good quantitative agreement, probably due to experimental
257 inaccuracies or uncontrolled factors (**Figure S4**). Even this outlier rejected the null model, showing a
258 trend consistent with our hypothesis (**Figure S4**).

259

260

261 **Figure 4: The response to mixed food patches follows the same trend. (A)** Relative number of worms in
 262 patches of DA1885 and CR266, as a function of bacterial density (measured in OD). Our experiment will
 263 take place at OD=0.5 (black dashed line), where DA1885 is about 10 times more attractive than CR266
 264 (circles). Our null model predicts an average response for a 50:50 mixture of both species (black
 265 errorbar, whose bottom is the geometric mean and whose top is the arithmetic mean of the two
 266 circles). **(B)** Relative number of worms in a food patch, as a function of its effective bacterial density
 267 (D/D_0). Circles: Effective density for CR266 and DA1885 at OD=0.5, and their corresponding predicted
 268 relative number of worms. Red cross: Effective bacterial density for a 50:50 mixture of CR266 and
 269 DA1885 at OD=0.5, and its predicted relative number of worms. **(C)** Experimental scheme: Worms are
 270 exposed to 5 food patches with different fractions of CR266 and 1885, always at OD=0.5, and counted
 271 after 2 hours. **(D)** Number of worms at each food patch, as a fraction of DA1885. Dots: Experimental
 272 results (errorbars show the 95% confidence interval). Red line: Prediction from our model. Gray patch:
 273 Prediction of the null model.

274

275 **Discussion**

276 Our results show that *C. elegans*' response to food is driven by the number of cells encountered per unit
277 area, with other factors such as bacterial species and biomass content having minimal effect. This
278 observation suggests that the neural circuit responsible for most of *C. elegans*' response to food is
279 driven by food consumption, and independent of chemical cues.

280 While we found a striking similarity in the response of *C. elegans* to all bacterial species, we do not claim
281 that worms respond identically to all of them. First, we did find some differences in the response to
282 different species: First, the collapse of our results when using bacterial density in cells/mm² is worse
283 than when using D0. Second, we also found significant differences in the other sigmoid parameters. For
284 some bacterial species, such as CR13, these differences are significant. However, one limitation of our
285 study is that, despite our best efforts to achieve sufficient throughput, our results still have large
286 uncertainty. Also, we were unable to completely eliminate day-to-day variability, and we found that
287 parameters H and k are relatively sensitive to uncontrolled conditions. Therefore, while we believe that
288 at least some of the differences across species that remain in our results are real (in particular for CR13),
289 we cannot rule out the possibility that they are due to experimental inaccuracies.

290 Our experimental design minimized the effect of any chemical cues: Bacteria had no nutrients to fuel
291 their metabolism, and bacteriostatic antibiotics prevented their growth. This will not be the case in
292 many natural conditions, where chemical cues may modify worm behavior significantly. However, our
293 results indicate that the effect of chemical cues can be decoupled experimentally, and by doing so we
294 have discovered a core foraging mechanism that seems independent of chemical signaling.
295 Furthermore, in most comparable cases our results are similar to those of other studies where bacterial
296 metabolism was not inhibited [REFS]. A notable exception is the case of *S. marcescens*, a known
297 pathogen for *C. elegans* [REFS], but for palatable species such as *E. coli* our results are compatible with
298 previous studies [REFS]. This compatibility suggests that the core mechanism identified in this study is
299 responsible for most of the foraging behavior of *C. elegans*.

300 Etc.

301 **Materials and Methods**

302 In preparation

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360

361 **Supplementary Figures**

362

363 **Figure S1: Sigmoids of all species.** Relative number of worms found at each food patch (N/N_{ref}), as a function of
 364 bacterial density in the food patch (D , measured in OD). Dots: Experimental data; errorbars show the 95%
 365 confidence interval. Lines: Best-fitting sigmoid. Semitransparent patches: 95% confidence interval for the fitted
 366 sigmoids. Six species were measured twice, with about two years between both measurements, and with each
 367 measurement performed in a different laboratory. Five out of the six species provided compatible results. One
 368 species (CR164) provided incompatible results between both experiments. This species is also the one whose
 369 results in the mixed drops did not match our predictions (**Figure S4**).

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372 **Figure S2: Sigmoid parameters for all species. (A)** Best-fitting value of H for each sigmoid, and 95%
 373 confidence interval. **(B)** Best-fitting value of D₀ for each sigmoid, and 95% confidence interval. **(C)** Best-
 374 fitting value of k for each sigmoid, and 95% confidence interval.

375

376 **Figure S3: Fitness: In preparation**

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 379 **Figure S4: Results from mixed drops.** Each column corresponds to one pair of species. **(A)** Goodness of
 380 fit of our prediction to the experimental data, for each possible value of D_0 for each species (hotter
 381 color means better fit). Circle: Experimental D_0 , obtained from an independent experiment (orange
 382 sigmoids in **Figure S1**). Cross: Values of D_0 that best reproduce the mixed-drop experiments. In the last
 383 two pairs, the experimental values are very close to the best-fitting one. In the first pair the optimal
 384 value is far from the experimental one, but the experimental values are still on the region of excellent fit
 385 (yellow region). In the second pair the fit is not good: The experimental values fall outside the good
 386 fitting region. This pair involves species CR164, which also gave a sigmoid significantly different to the
 387 one originally measured (see **Figure S1**), so it's likely that experimentally uncontrolled factors were
 388 responsible for this mismatch. **(B)** Number of worms at each food patch, as a fraction of one of the
 389 species. Dots: Experimental results (errorbars show the 95% confidence interval). Red line: Prediction
 390 from our model, using the experimentally measured D_0 's (circle in box A). Gray patch: Prediction of the
 391 null model. **(C)** Same as B, but prediction uses the best-fitting values of D_0 .

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